

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B113
Date: 20/07/2005
Take Off 07:34:05
Landing: 12:33:34
Flight Time 4h59m29

Campaign: AMPEP
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Bristol Channel, S coast & E Coast up to Teeside

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottoway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Ute Skiba	CEH
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	CCM2/Filters/CVI	Paul James	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM
8	AMS	Hugh Coe	Manchester University
9	AMS training	Gerrard Capes	Manchester University
10	Core chem / TDLAS	Alan Woolley	FAAM
11	Bags 1	Alan Harrison	Met Office
12	Bags 2	Mark Theobald	CEH
13	Ptr-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
14	Ptr-MS training	Jennifer Murphy	UEA
15	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B113 Track 20-JUL-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b113

Date: 20/07/05

Project: AMPEP

Location: Bristol Channel, S coast & E coast to Teeside

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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070016		Start posn	0.20 kft	125	52'04.36N,0'37.48W
071736		INU	0.19 kft	125	To NAVIGATE
073405		T/O	3.3 kft	024	Cranfield
073855		ASPs	7.9 kft	030	Open
073940		Videos	10.0 kft		Start FFC & RFC
074043		NOXY	10.0 kft	345	Cals
083418	083902	Profile 1	10.1 - 6.0 kft	140	1000fpm
083902	084018	Run 1	6.0 - 6.1 kft	137	
084018	084244	Profile 1	6.1 - 4.0 kft	138	
084244	084431	Run 2	4.0 - 2.7 kft	139	To 2000'
084606	084701	Profile 1	2.5 - 1.7 kft	137	QNH 1025mB
084701	084814	Run 3	1.7 kft	138	2000'
084815	084923	Profile 1	1.7 - 0.71 kft	136	2000'- 1000'
084923	085034	Run 4	0.71 - 0.70 kft	090	1000'
085035	085134	Profile 1	0.70 - 0.18 kft	084	1000'- 500'
085134	085235	Run 5	0.18 - 0.20 kft	089	500'
085236	085335	Profile 1	0.19 - -.20 kft	090	500'- 100'
085335	085428	Run 6	-.20 kft	090	100'
085541	090246	Run 7.1	0.66 - 0.68 kft	083	1000', QNH 1025
090228		EVM	0.66 kft	071	WP45
090306	091644	Run 7.2	0.69 - 0.73 kft	039	End @ WP44
091056		EVM	0.74 kft	038	QNH 1023mB
091711	093109	Run 7.3	0.71 - 0.76 kft	091	End @ WP43
092300		NOXY			No O2, switched OFF
093040		EVM	0.82 kft	090	QNH 1021mB
093118	094252	Run 7.4	0.76 - 0.81 kft	058	End @ WP42
094320	095715	Run 7.5	0.82 - 0.84 kft	006	End @ WP41,Q1020
095250		EVM	0.83 kft	005	QNH 1019mB
095715	101139	Run 7.6	0.84 - 0.87 kft	004	End @ WP40
101139	102308	Run 7.7	0.87 - 0.89 kft	330	End @ WP87
101517		EVM	0.93 kft	317	QNH 1017mB
102308	104536	Run 7.8	0.89 - 0.90 kft	296	End @ WP80
102913		EVM	0.92 kft	316	Rain shower
103000	105000	AMS			No data, restarting
103852		Videos	0.91 kft	329	Change tapes
104536	110111	Run 7.9	0.90 kft	331	End @ WP80
110237	110524	Profile 2	0.93 - 0.01 kft	330	1000'- 100'
110524	110617	Run 8	0.01 - 0.08 kft	316	100'
110617	110701	Profile 3	0.08 - 0.40 kft	315	100'- 500'
110701	110752	Run 9	0.40 - 0.42 kft	332	500'
110752	110833	Profile 3	0.42 - 0.90 kft	337	500'- 1000'
110833	110925	Run 10	0.90 - 0.93 kft	340	1000'
110926	111054	Profile 3	0.93 - 1.9 kft	342	1000'- 2000'
111055	111144	Run 11	1.9 kft	343	2000'
					Turn South
111311	111555	Profile 3	1.9 - 4.0 kft	154	2000'- FL40
111555	111655	Run 12	4.0 kft	164	
111655	111902	Profile 3	4.0 - 6.0 kft	164	
111903	112018	Run 13	6.0 kft	141	
113158	120017	Run 14.1	0.94 - 0.87 kft	141	1000'
114135		EVM	0.91 kft	157	Q1017mB
115412		EVM	0.87 kft	152	QNH 1019mB
115648		EVM	0.87 kft	134	7nm abeam WP87
121611		ASPs	9.2 kft	255	Closed
123334		Land	0.16 kft	359	Cranfield
123746		Stop posn	0.15 kft	307	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

B113 Track 20-JUL-05

Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B113

Mission Scientist: Ute Skiba, CEH

Date 20-July-2005

Outline schedule:

05:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
07:00 – Briefing
07:55 – Clear aircraft and security check
08:30 – Doors close
09:00 – Take off Cranfield
13:00 – Land Teesside
15:00 – Takeoff Teesside
17:30 – Land Cranfield
18:30 – Debrief
19:00 – Power down

Location: A coastal transect of the South and East Coast of England

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols leaving the UK in gentle North Westerly airflow over the UK. The objective, in addition to measuring the export fluxes of pollutants is to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be obtained by flying off the South and East coasts along a coastal transect beginning in the Bristol Channel to sample background air off the coast of Cornwall. The transect of the UK outflow begins along the English Channel heading East to Dover then North to the point where airflow off the land stops, which according to current forecasts is North Yorkshire. Then after refueling (in Inverness) to return along the same East coast path to WP 40 off the Norfolk coast, returning to Cranfield. Vertical profiles (50 – 6000 ft) once upwind in the Bristol channel and downwind of the source region off the Yorkshire coast on the Southbound leg will provide the vertical structure in concentration and meteorology. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO. These measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region. Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags.

Sortie Detail with approx timing

- a) Take off Cranfield 09:00 and climb to 10000 ft for transit east to operating area. Destination waypoint 47 in the Bristol Channel; background filter run & NO_x calibration.
- b) T+20 Profile down to define the boundary layer structure off the coast with 1 min sampling at each height (6000, 4000, 2000, 1000, 500, 100)

- c) T+35 Return to 1000 ft for sampling..
Start of filter run No 1. Start of Bag sampling (1 bag every min) continue all the way up the east coast.
- d) T+160 background profile at point 74 (dip to 50ft, ascent at 1000 ft min⁻¹, level out at 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each, approx. 15 min profile duration)
- e) T+240 land Teesside
- f) T+360 T/O Teesside
- g) T+360 before leaving coast near WP87; downwind profile heading north (dip to 50ft, ascent at 1000 ft min⁻¹, level out at 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each, approx. 15 min profile duration); followed by NO_x calibration
- h) T+ 510 Land Cranfield

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 - Alan Roberts ?
2. Pilot 2 – Alan Foster ?
3. CCM – Sue Angold ?
4. CCM 2 Paul James
5. Cloud Physics – Jim Crawford
6. CVI Paul James
7. Flight Manager – Maureen Smith
8. Mission Scientist – Ute Skiba
9. Core Chemistry/TDLAS/PAN – Alan Woolley
10. Core Chemistry Training- ?
11. Filters- Paul James
12. WAS – Maria Nielsdottir
13. Bag Sampling 1 – Alan McDonald
14. Bag Sampling 2 – Mark Theobald
15. AMS – Keith Bower
16. PTRMS – Anne Hulse ?
17. PTRMS–Training Jennifer Murphy ?
18. NO_x –

MAPS:

Cranfield T/O 09:00
 47
 48
 46
 45
 44
 43
 42
 41
 40
 87
 80
 79
 Refuel at Teeside
 80
 87
 40
 Cranfield land 17:30

Monday 18 July 2005 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+060 VT: Wednesday 20 July 2005 12UTC
Surface: 2 metre temperature / 30 Metres Wind

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO_3 & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH_3). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value. Three 30-min runs of filters on each leg (S→N and N→S)

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO, SO_2 , NO and NO_2 will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at FL10.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

PTRMS: Operation as normal.

NO_x: Operation as normal; calibration during transits at FL100

WAS: Sampling density and location to be decided.

TDL for CH₄ and CO₂: Operated by FAAM.

Quick-look data: pressure height, lat, long, temp, RH, CN, SO₂, NO, NO₂, O₃, CO

Flightpath: Cranfield into Bristol Channel at 10,000 feet, here one profile to 100 feet, then climbing to 1000 feet and maintaining this height through the English Channel – North Sea to WP79, around here a profile to 500, 100, 5000, 1000, 2000, 4000, 6000 feet was carried out before returning to 1000 feet and returning along the coast to Cromar. From here we returned to 10,000 feet and returned to Cranfield.

Weather conditions: Cloudy, with showers from WP87 onwards, increasing in frequency during the day, which caused interference with AMS data on the return journey. The wave pattern suggested a ground level wind speed of force 4 at WP87. The wind direction changed towards a more northerly sector for some period between 10:30 – 11: 30 GMT, which meant that we did not ‘see’ the Teesside plume on the outward journey.

Problems: NO_x and O₃ only operated for the first hour of flying. AMS was not working around WP80. On the homeward journey when SO₂, NO_x and CO instruments showed large plumes the AMS could not see these plumes, due to rain showers downwind.

Profiles and plumes The ‘background’ profile of SO₂, NO_x and CO in the Bristol Channel showed very small increases in concentrations with decreasing height. Back at 100 feet low concentrations were maintained until around WP41. From then on concentrations in the above mentioned gases increased, with occasional large peaks some associated with shipping activity. Concentrations increased after WP87 until maximum concentrations were measured downwind of Yorkshire. The Teesside plume as predicted by NAME was not observed on the outward journey due to changes in wind direction. Does the Yorkshire plume contain Teesside pollution?, this needs to be checked. At Teesside and north concentrations were low and a second profile was carried out. Here concentration differences between heights were larger compared to those in the Bristol Channel. On the return journey from Teesside to Cromar plumes were ‘seen’ downwind of Teesside and Yorkshire. The Yorkshire plume pattern was very similar on the outward and return journey.

Ute Skiba

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.113**
 GMT

 Date **20.7.05**

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EST GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
8:30	Start	at Cranfield.			light cloud cover, sunny Windy
8:55		NOxy problems.			
	at 10000ft	in cloud		over	Bristol.
Profile 1		around 8:32	->	complete	cloud cover below
08:39					
8:	Run 1	6000			Cloud - continuous
8:42		4000			cloud now broken
		2000		NOx - 0.6 SO ₂ 0.27	CO 82 below cloud
8:47		1000		NOx - 0.4 SO ₂ 0.27	CO 86
8:52		500		NOx 0.3 SO ₂ - 0.05	CO 86
8:54		100		NOx - 0.01 SO ₂ 0.27	CO 85
8:55	Run 7	1000			Continuous cloud cover above shipping activity at 9:00 and CO ₂ increased ^{just} before WP45
9:02				WP45 now to 44	etc (also a broader peak of NOx)
9:16					ship downwind, ^{small} increase in CO
					NO NOxy measurements for rest of flight.
9:28					steady increase in NOx due to shipping activity ^{and off land} . + SO ₂ (CO sharp peak due to calibration)
9:31	point 43				
9:45	Run 7.5 to point 41				shipping activity at Dover (followed by small blip in SO ₂)
9:51 to 9:56		large		NOx SO ₂ plumes and smaller CO plume.	
9:57	at 41	Run 7.6			
10:05				diffuse	smoke at least - resulting in small NOx peak just before Lovestoff.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.113**.....

 Date **20.7.05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:19					Wave pattern suggests Force 4 winds
10:23	7.8			87	
10:27					increase in NOx
10:29	- 10:32				in rain shower
10:33	- 10:38				downwind of 'leeds' etc = plumes of SO ₂ , NOx, CO
10:33					shower now to our right.
10:36					Manpack lnt filament and not operating for next 30 min. i.e. missed the 'leeds' plume
10:38					plume
10:40					rain showers to our left (downwind)
10:43					low clouds, we are still below.
10:43					v. light rain + ^{show} SO ₂ plume,
10:45	7.9	point 80			
10:52					RMS up in morning again
10:58					rain unfortunately Teeside plume was overland
Profile	11:03	descend to 500 feet			shower downwind
Run 8	~ 11:05	100 feet			lot fish jumping.
Run 9	11:07	500 feet			SO ₂ 2.77 NOx 0.44 CO 9.7
R 10	11:08:30	1000 feet			SO ₂ 1.77 ^{0.87} NOx 0.44 ^{-0.08} CO 8.9
R 11	11:10:54	2000 feet			SO ₂ 0.17 NOx -0.8 CO 8.7
R 12	11:11:46	turn round to			complete profile.
R	11:13:11	2700 feet.			SO ₂ 0.07 CO 8.8 NOx -0.7
					just below cloud now

CLLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B113

Date: 20 July 2005

Operator: Jim Crawford

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
06:33											Preflight complete – satis
07:37											Heaters on – after t/o
08:20	152	0.77	221		67	175	11	0	0		FI100 (transit)
08:22	3	0.08	248		0	0		0	0		
08:24	3	0.08	248		0	0		0	0		Clear air above cloud
08:26	7	0.07	248		0	0		0	0		
08:28	2	0.1	248		0	0		0	0		
08:30	1	0.08	248		0	0		0	0		
08:32	13	0.11	248		0	0		0	0		
08:34	26	0.08	248		0	0		0	0		
08:35:45	24	0.08	248		0	0		0	0		P1 fl90
08:36:45	4	0.07	248		0	0		0	0		P1 fl80
08:37:45	4	0.07	248		0	0		0	0		P1 fl70
08:38:45	94	0.53	297		3	0	12	25	0		R1 fl60
08:41:32	41	0.35	508		0	0		0	0		P1 fl50
08:42:44	46	0.1	515		0	0		0	0		R2 fl40
08:45:55	66	0.09	515		0	0		0	0		P1 3000ft
08:47:04	80	0.1	515		0	0		0	0		R3 2000ft
08: 49:30	154	0.1	515		0	0		0	0		R4 1000ft
08:51:30	363	0.08	515		0	0		0	0		R5 500ft
08:53:35	229	0.1	516		0	0		0	0		R6 100ft
08:56:00	123	0.09	516		0	0		0	0		R7.1 1000ft
09:00:00	100	0.09	516								Clear air
09:04:00	106	0.11	516								
09:08:00	119	0.09	516								
09:12:00	102	0.1	516								
09:14:00	89	0.1	516								
09:16:00	121	0.1	516								

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B113

Date:20 July 05

Operator:Jim Crawford

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:18:00	150	0.1	516								
09:20:00	174	0.1	517								
09:22:00	108	0.09	517								
09:24:00	207	0.09	517								
09:26:00	154	0.1	517								
09:28:00	121	0.09	517								
09:30:00	127	0.08	517								
09:32:00	74	0.08	517								
09:34:00	116	0.09	517								
09:36:00	152	0.09	517								
09:38:00	185	0.08	517								
09:40:00	212	0.09	517								
09:42:00	157	0.08	517								
09:44:00	254	0.08	517								
09:46:00	260	0.08	517								
09:48:00	155	0.08	517								
09:50:00	127	0.09	517								
09:52:00	143	0.08	517								
09:54:00	140	0.08	517								
09:56:00	196	0.08	517								
09:58:00	132	0.1	517								
10:00:00	129	0.09	517								
10:02:00	182	0.08	517								
10:04:00	266	0.09	517								
10:06:00	223	0.09	517								
10:08:00	154	0.08	517								
10:10:00	214	0.08	517								
10:12:00	237	0.08	517								
10:14:00	161	0.1	517								
10:16:00	204	0.09	517								
10:18:00	173	0.09	517								

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B113

Date:20 July 2005

Operator:Jim Crawford

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:20:00	176	0.08	517								
10:22:00	237	0.08	517								
10:24:00	200	0.07	517								
10:26:00	216	0.07	517								
10:28:00	215	0.08	517								
10:30:00	275	0.08	517		1	0	1	416	0		
10:32:00	228	0.15	517								
											Fifos seen as reset on fssp
											Probe power cycled now ok
10:36:00											Fssp recycled again
10:40:00	214	0.07	517								
10:42:00	210	0.07	517								
10:44:00	222	0.06									Fssp recycled
10:46:00	171	0.06	517								
10:48:00	184	0.08	517								
10:50:00	116	0.07	517								
10:52:00	129	0.08	517								
10:54:00	134	0.08	517								
10:56:00	124	0.07	517								
10:58:00	141	0.08	517								
11:00:00	112	0.13	519		6.5	0	1	375	0		
11:02:00	120	0.07	522								
11:05:20	140	0.07	524								R8 100ft
11:07:11	257	0.06	524								R9 500ft
11:08:40	25	0.08	524								R10 1000ft
11:10:55	82	0.07	524								R11 2000ft
11:14:11	103	0.07	524								P3 3000ft
11:16:00	258	0.07	530		1	0	1	8	0		R12 fl40

Flight No. B113Route Date 20/07/2005Take Off 730 GMTBag Samplers: M. THEOBALD M. HARRISONSheet No. 1

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
052	7:44:00	7:46:30	S 2.3N	0.5W	10.0 kft.
424	7:47:00	7:47:30	S 2.2	0.7W	
342	7:50:00	7:50:30		1.0W	
496	7:53:00	7:53:30		1.5W	
172	7:56:00	7:56:30			
012	7:58:00	7:59:30	S 1.9	1.8W	
123	8:02:00	8:02:30	S 1.8	2.0W	
003	8:05	8:05:30	S 1.6	2.2W	
498	8:08:00	8:08:30			Sampling thru cloud
26	8:11:00	8:11:30			cloud
271	8:29:05	8:29:35	S 0.4	4.0W	cloud top = 6 kft
011	8:41:05	8:41:35			5.5-0.5-0
29	8:42:50	8:43:20	S 0.2	3.7W	= 11 kft
214	8:43:10	8:43:40	S 0.1	3.6W	3.4-0.8
50	8:47:05	8:47:35	S 0.0	3.5W	= 1.7 kft
52	8:49:15				
175	8:49:35	8:50:05	S 0.0	3.3W	= 0.7 kft
203	8:51:36	8:52:06			= 5.0 5.0 kft
70	8:53:37	8:54:07			1.7 kft
241	8:56:00	8:56:30	S 0.0	2.6W	1.000 ft.
67	8:57:00	8:57:30			
457	8:58:00	8:58:30			
37	8:59:00	8:59:30			
185	9:00:00	9:00:30			
370	9:01:00	01:30	S 0.0	2.0W	Way - Point 45.
243	2:00	2:30			
38	3:00	3:30			
255	4:00	4:30			
293	5:00	5:30			
151	6:00	6:30			
411	7:00	7:30			
59	8:00	8:30			
41	9:00	9:30	S 0.3N	1.5W	
588	10:00	10:30			
353	9:11	9:11:30			
214	9:12	9:12:30			
253	9:13	9:13:30			
517	9:14	9:14:30			
308	9:15	9:15:30			
425	9:16	16:30			Wave 44.
555	9:17	17:30			

in cloud
under cloud

Flight No. Route Date Take Off Bag Samplers: Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
551	9.18	9:18:20			
15	9.19 9.19	19:30			
552	9.20	20:30			
109	9.21	21:30			
318	9.22	22:30			
23	9.23	23:30			50.6N 0.3W
15	9.24	24:30			
520	9.25	25:30			
27	9.26	26:30			
317	9.27	27:30			
157	9.28	28:30			
603	9.29	29:30			
401	9.30	30:30	50.6	0.3E	
154	9.31	31:30			
259	9.32	32:30			
439	9.33	33:30			
453	9.34	34:30			
602	9.35	35:30	50.7N	0.8E	
181	9.36	36:30			
155	9.37	37:30			
280	9.38	38:30			
605	9.39	39:30			
608	9.40	40:30			
33	9.41	9.41-27	50.9	1.3E	
138	9.42	9.42-28			Waypoint 43
117	9.43	43:30			
118	9.44	44:30			
24	9.45	45:30			
350	9.46	46:30			
153	9.47	47:30			
438	9.48	48:30			
111	9.49	49:30			
352	9.50	50:30			
137	9.51	51:30			
629	9.52	52:30			
159	9.53	53:30			
315	9.54	54:30			
377	9.55	55:30			
284	9.56	9.56-31			
550	9.57	57:30			
609	9.58	58:30			

Flight No. B113Route Date 20.7.05Take Off 17:30Bag Samplers: M. THEOBALD + M. HARRISONSheet No. 3

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
601	9.59	59.30			
281	10.00	10:00:30			
302	10.01	01:30			
607	10.02	02:30			
89	10.03	03:30			
442	10.04	04:30			
158	10.05	05:30			Smoke plume - bank
354	10.06	06:30			
249	10.07	07:30			
136	10.08	08:30			
243	10.09	09:30			
135	10.10	10:30			
134	10.11	11:30			Point 40.
160	10.12	12:30			
110	10.13	13:30	52.7	1.7E	
601	10.14	14:30			
152	10.15	15:30			
244	10.16	10.16.35			
628	10.17	17:30			
606	10.18	18:30			
278	10.19	19:30			
156	10.20	20:30			
135	10.21	21:30			
116	10.22	22:30			Point 87
114	10.23	23:30			
183	10.24	24:30	53.0	0.9E	
516	10.25	25:30			
623	10.26	26:30			
108	10.27	27:30			
614	10.28	28:30			Point 87?
113	10.29	29:30			Rain
45	10.30	30:30			
620	10.31	31:30	53.3	0.6E	
44	10.32	10.32.31			
624	10.33	33:30			
54	10.34	34:30			
65	10.35	35:30			
120	10.36	36:30			
86	10.37	37:30			
140	10.38	38:30			
99	10.39	39:30			

Flight No. B113 Route

Date 20705 Take Off 7:30

Bag Samplers: M THORP + M. HARRISON

Sheet No. 21

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
535	10:40	40:30	53.8N	0.2E	
96	10:41	41:30			
621	10:42	42:30			
31	10:43	43:30			
35	10:44	44:30			
600	10:45	45:30	54.0N	0.0E	
102	10:46	46:30			
627	10:47	47:30			
93	10:48	48:30			
112	10:49	49:30			
106	10:50	50:30			
104	10:51	51:30			
100	10:52	52:30			
612	10:53	53:30	54.3	0.3W.	
95	10:54	54:30			
625	10:55	55:30			
107	10:56	56:30			
91	10:57	57:30			
162	58	58:30			
611	59	59:30			
101	11:00	11:00:30			
610	11:01	11:01:30			
115	11:05:30	11:06:00	54.8N	1.0W	100ft
32	11:07:05	11:07:35			500ft
619	11:08:35	11:09:05			1000ft
120	11:09:40	11:10:10			1-2000ft
97	11:11:00	11:11:30	55.0	1.2W	2000ft
451	11:14:10	11:14:40			2.6kft - 2.8kft
622	11:16:00	11:16:30			4000 in cloud
48	11:17:35	11:18:05			4.7kft - 5.1kft (out of cloud)
617	11:19:05	11:19:35			6kft
133	11:37:00	11:37:30			FIRST BAG OF RUN
083	11:38:00	11:38:30	54.0N	0.1E	
626	39:00	39:30			
618	40:00	40:30			
615	41:00	41:30			
427	42:00	42:30			
046	43:00	43:30			
310	44:00	44:30	53.7N	0.4E	

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 20/7/05

FLIGHT: B113

OPERATOR: MC / GC.

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:	
Power ON	Ensure Inlet Closed	Inlet Valve	✓		04:30 LOCAL	
	Ensure Multiplier Off	Electronics box	✓			
	Ensure Heater Off	Electronics box	✓			
	Ensure all Pumps Off	Pump Control box	✓			
	Turn on 230V Breaker	Power unit on a/c wall	✓			
	Turn on:	Electronics box power	✓	NOTICED ALL RED LEDS FLASHED ON WHEN POWER UP		
		Diaphragm pump power	✓			
		Turbo pump power	✓			
		CPC Power, both Buttons	✓			
		Open backing pump valve	Front facing side of rack.	✓		
		Turn on Alcatel... 100% speed	Pump Control Box, after #6	✓	NO PUMP LIGHTS COME ON BUT POWER ON TURBOS Monitor Pump Currents OK?	
		Turbo pumps 2 and 3 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box			
	Turbo pumps 4 and 5 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box				
	Turbo pump 6 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box				
	Plug in CPC fill bottle	Rear of CPC	✓			
	Turn on heater	Electronics box	✓	Approx 2.8V, 0.9A	04:55 LOCAL	
Pre-Brief	Turn on Balzers Box	Power distribution box and Balzers box	✓			
	Turn on Copper	Electronics box	✓	Approx 125Hz	115Hz.	
	Turn on PC/Monitor	Power distribution box and PC	✓			
	Start AMS software	PC Desktop	✓			
	Turn autosaving off	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓	NEGATIVE NUMBER		
	Reduce Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓			
	Set filament to 0.00mA, Scan range 0-300amu	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓			
	Turn Multiplier on	Electronics box	✓			
	Turn filament on @0.05mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓			DONE @ 06:05. LOCAL

04:30 POWER ON
05:45 PRE BRIEF
06:30 BRIEFING.

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 20/7/05

FLIGHT: B113

OPERATOR: HC/GC.

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Post Brief	Increase Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV ✓	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓		
	Close Grimm valve	Inlet valve	✓	wait on	
	CPC in low flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Check RF box, Tune if needed	Turn Tune Screw on RF Box for best hit	✓		
	Log CPC on AMS serial port 2	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Open AMS inlet	Inlet valve	✓		
	Increase filament to 2.5mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓		
	Toggle chopper in MS mode	Press T within MS mode	✓		
	Check Airbeams and flows	Add m28 to m/z selection, Clean pin hole???	✓	F=1.9, AB approx 2.3MHz	f=1.9 2.3 MHz
	Tune Balzers	Software	✓	Ensure no major changes	
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Gain approx 3e6	2.8 x 10 ⁶
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	15,16,17,30,46*	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling, Calibrate, Save, Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1, a=0.41, 350nm	
	Remove CPC butanol from aircraft	Rear of CPC	✓		
	CPC in high flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Reconnect inlet and GRIMM	Inlet	✓		
	Set CPC port=0 in AMS software	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓	LOG CPC IN LABVIEW ✓	
	Set PC time with Horace	Desktop plus internet explorer	✓		
	Set mass range scan	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		0-300
	Select tof masses to scan	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	14,16,30,43,44,46,48,57	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Set DC marker 3 pos=6200	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Backup parameter file	C:\AMS\AMSCODE\AMSMENU.prm	✓		
	Set save interval	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓	0.5 minutes????	
	Reconnect inlet, Close AMS valve	Inlet	✓		
	Start CPC software	PC Desktop	✓		
General Alteration mode, Open Inlet	Software, Start after t/o	✓			

AMS Calibration Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 20/7/2005 FLIGHT: B113

OPERATOR: WC/CC

Tuning

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner	28	30	22
Def Outer	16	16	11
Heater Bias	-6.7	-6.94	-6.5
Focus	15.50	15	12.5
Extraction	200	236	220

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner			22
Def Outer			11
Heater Bias			-6.5
Focus			12.5
Extraction			220

Multiplier Cal

Might have to tweak filament current and multiplier voltage in order to set thresholds in calibration!!!!
This is done in the parameter menu..... Multiplier and Chopper Tab

TIME:	New	Typical
KV		n/a
KV Change		0.025kV
Gain		3.00E+06
G used Change		1

TIME:	New	Typical
KV	2.5	n/a
KV Change	0.0	0.025kV
Gain	2.94	3.00E+06
G used Change	0.80	1

Ionization Efficiency Cal

TIME:	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	1.89×10^6	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.8	4
IPP NO3	439	400
IPP NH4	455	550
Airbeam MS	2.1×10^6	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	7.3×10^5	2.00E+06
Run Number		n/a

TIME:	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	2.27×10^6	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.77	4
IPP NO3	529	400
IPP NH4	579	550
Airbeam MS	2.66×10^6	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	9.5×10^5	2.00E+06
Run Number	3153	n/a

Filter Run

TIME:	
Run number	

TIME:	
Run number	

AMS Diagnostic Log Sheet v2.00

DATE:

FLIGHT:

OPERATOR:

Time 0820

(No sig. change) 0900

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.79	0.86	88	98
2	2.99	3.5	100	100
3	1.30	1	100	100
4	0.59	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.43	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.82	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	587	580
Heater B	72.6	75V
Multiplier	—	n/a
Pressure	1.409	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	7	7A
I diaphragm	1.2	2A
MS AB	1.85	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.88	2Mhz
Flow	1.47	2

Time 09:30

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.92	0.86	87	98
2	3.47	3.5	100	100
3	1.35	1	100	100
4	0.60	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.43	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.82	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	588	580
Heater B	72.7	75V
Multiplier	2.44	n/a
Pressure	1.833	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	7.5	7A
I diaphragm	1.2	2A
MS AB	2.29	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	2.13	2Mhz
Flow	2.06	2

Time

10:55

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.82	0.86	0.88	98
2	3.47	3.5	100	100
3	1.36	1	100	100
4	0.65	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.43	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.77	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	568	580
Heater B	72	75V
Multiplier	—	n/a
Pressure	1.83	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	7	7A
I diaphragm	1.2	2A
MS AB	2.27	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	2.07	2Mhz
Flow	2.04	2

Time

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel		0.86		98
2		3.5		100
3		1		100
4		0.5		100
5		0.4		100
6		0.46		100

	New	Typical
Heater V		2.5
Heater I		0.9
Heater T		580
Heater B		75V
Multiplier		n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics		1A
I turbo		7A
I diaphragm		2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

AMIS PostFlight Setup/Cal Sheet V2.00

DATE:

FLIGHT:

OPERATOR:

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Pre-land	Stop AMS,Grimm CPC logging	Software	✓		
	Close AMS inlet	Inlet	✓		
	Exit Labview		✓		
	Enable CPC in AMS software	Parameter Menu, Serial Ports tab	✓		
Post-land	Set CPC in Low Flow	Shift+totalizer on CPC display	✓		
	Open Inlet		✓		
	Turn off autosave (-ve number)	Parameter Menu,Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Check gain at current V	
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓	15,16,17,30,46*	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling,Calibrate,Save,Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1,a=0.41,350nm	
	Attach Zero filter to inlet		✓		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓	14,16,30,43,44,46,48,57	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓		
General alteration,10 mins	Software, F3 to NonAutoSave	✓	Check tof windows ?		
Close inlet		✓			
Data	Copy AutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy NonAutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\NonAutoSaveDate	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy AMSLogFiles folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AMSLogFiles	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy CPC data	Source C:\UCPC\	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Backup directory to DVD/laptop				
	Delete AutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	✓
Delete NonAutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	✓	
Delete AMSLogFiles	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	✓	
Delete CPC data	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	✓	
ShutDown	Turn off Mulitplier & Balzers	Electronics box	✓		
	Turn off all Turbos and PC	Pump Controller Box	✓		
	Shut Backing Valve	Back of rack	✓		
	Turn off heater,chopper,the rest	Electronics box, then power unit and Breakers	✓		

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B113**

Date: 20/07/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	N	
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	y	N
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI		N
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	Y
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	Y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO	Y	Y	Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	N
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	Y
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	Y
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B113

Date: 12/07/05

Instruments

1. Upper Pyrometer – zero signal following radiance signal
2. NOXY – Nitric Acid channel very noisy – unusable on initial transit
3. TWC – Status light flashing at 100ft (~0854Z). Then okay.
4. NOXY – ran out of oxygen at 0923Z. Shut down instrument so no more data.
5. AMS – lost filament current, reset then okay (but no data from 1030 to 1050Z)
6. Flt. Manager's display – Flight Summary window bombed out numerous times. Closed all iExplorer windows and re-opened to clear the problem.
7. Cloud Physics -FFSSP reset itself a couple of times otherwise okay. SID1 Not operated.

Other Instruments: PtRms, Core Chemistry & Filters - fine

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom H – not used

New plot, same times

Flight B113 12:02:05

Heading 242 deg Speed 215 knots Height 5.2kft Press 835mb

Lat 52.8N Long 1.3E Wind 19 ms-1/ 317 deg

Temp 4.0C Dewpoint -1.51C

From 07:14:53 to now

Current values				
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	43323	secs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All
—	OZONE MIXING RATIO	26.8	ppb	<input type="checkbox"/>
—	TECO SO2	0.47	ppb	<input type="checkbox"/>
—	TECO NO	0.14	ppb	<input type="checkbox"/>
—	TECO NO2	0.78	ppb	<input type="checkbox"/>

New plot, same times

Flight B113 12:01:01

Heading 215 deg Speed 222 knots Height 1.8kft Press 945mb

Lat 52.9N Long 1.4E Wind 17 ms-1/ 300 deg

Temp 11.71C Dewpoint 7.01C

From 07:14:53 to now

Current values		
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	43260 secs
—	OZONE MIXING RATIO	10.87 ppb
—	TECO SO2	0.67 ppb
—	TECO NO	1.29 ppb
—	TECO NO2	1.73 ppb

New plot, same times

Flight B113 12:02:31

Heading 242 deg Speed 220 knots Height 6.6kft Press 793mb

Lat 52.8N Long 1.3E Wind 16 ms-1/ 310 deg

Temp 1.16C Dewpoint -3.5C

From 07:12:58 to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 43350 secs
CO MIXING RATIO 86.77 pbb

